

LITERARY NORMS AND SPEECH CULTURE

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ANNOTATION: Speech culture studies the literary norm in order to define the boundaries and means of cultural speech with a specific purpose. Therefore, the field of speech culture evaluates and monitors literary language and its normative system. The literary norm or linguistic norm or linguistic standard or language norm is a historically determined set of commonly used language assets, as well as rules for their selection and use, which have been recognized by society as the most appropriate in a particular historical period.

In this aspect the speech norm may be defined as a form of self-control of the speaker which correlates with his idea of the expectations of the other members of the group concerning the peculiarities of his speech. In its gnoceological aspect "speech culture" is a special area of linguistic knowledge, a scientific discipline containing definite units, subunits and rules devoted to that field of linguistics.

KEY WORDS: Standard, standard forms, , spelling, accent, pronunciation, punctuation, lexical, grammatical, Stylistic , rules of thinking words.

Nowadays, education lays a lot of emphasis on the importance of speech and communication culture in an individual's growth and formation. Language can introduce education into culture, but for the time being, education and culture are two interrelated processes. the cultural setting. Throughout human history, language has played a crucial part in social interactions. growing. The amount of information in circulation per capital might serve as a gauge for the degree of evolution of a community. The aim of this piece of literature is to examine the characteristics of culture and the prerequisites for communication efficacy. This work's primary objectives are analyze the research topic's literature, in order to highlight the key ideas.

Language is a reflection of culture; it reflects not only the actual environment in which an individual lives, but also the public consciousness of the populace, including their national character, mentality, way of life, traditions, customs, morality, value system, attitude, and vision of peace. It is a pantry, or repository, of cultural treasures. Cultural values are stored in its vocabulary, in grammar, in proverbs, sayings, in folklore, in fiction and scientific literature, in forms of written and oral speech.

Language is not only a means of communication and expression of thought, but also the accumulation of cultural values. One of the most important indicators of the level of human culture, his thinking, intelligence is his speech. Well-developed speech is one of the most important means of active human activity in modern society. Speech is a way of knowing reality. On the one hand, the richness of speech depends to a large extent on the enrichment of a person with new ideas and concepts; on the other hand, a good command of the language and speech contributes to the successful knowledge of complex relationships in nature and in the life of society. Speech is one of the types of communication that people need in their joint activities, in social life, the exchange of information, in cognition, in education, it enriches a person spiritually, serves as a subject of art.

The culture of speech, as a rule, is understood as a concept common in Soviet and Russian linguistics of the 20th century, which combines the knowledge of the language norm of oral and written language, as well as "the ability to use expressive language means in different communication conditions".

The concept of speech is closely related to language. Speech is "concrete speaking, taking place in time and clothed in sound (including internal pronunciation) or written form. Speech is commonly understood as the process of speaking itself, and the result of this process, i.e. both speech activity and speech works, fixed by memory or writing" Speech is perceived, concrete and unique, deliberate and directed towards a specific goal, it is situational, subjective and arbitrary. In speech, the functions of language appear in various combinations with the predominance of one of them. Communication between people is both a socio-psychological interaction and a channel for transmitting information. Therefore, textbooks on the culture of speech use the term communication. Communication - communication between people, the process of exchanging information, a process that supports the functioning of society and interpersonal relationships.

Communication consists of communicative acts in which communicants (the author and addressee .of the message) participate, generate statements (texts) and interpret them. The process of communication begins with the intention of the speaker and aims at understanding the utterance by the addressee.

The speech culture of society is the selection, collection and storage of the best examples of speech activity, the formation of literary classics and adherence to the norms of the literary language. Rozhdestvensky adheres to this understanding of speech culture. Of course, within the framework of the science of the culture of speech, not only examples of a high level of mastery of literary norms and rules of communication are considered, but also cases of violation of norms, both in the speech activity of an individual and in the speech practice of society.

Language norms are not invented by philologists, they reflect a certain stage in the development of the literary language of the whole people. The norms of the language cannot be introduced or canceled by decree; they cannot be reformed by administrative means. The activity of linguists who study language norms is different: they identify, describe and codify language norms, as well as explain and promote them.

The main sources of the language norm include:

- the works of classical writers;
- works by contemporary writers who continue the classical traditions;
- media publications;
- common modern usage;
- linguistic research data.

Characteristic features of language norms are: relative stability; prevalence; general use; general obligation; conformity with the use, custom and possibilities of the language system. Norms help the literary language to maintain its integrity and general intelligibility. They protect the literary language from the flow of dialect speech, social and professional jargon, and vernacular. This allows the literary language to perform one of the most important functions - cultural. A speech norm is a set of the most stable traditional implementations of a language system, selected and fixed in the process of public communication. The normalization of speech is its correspondence .

Until the end of the twentieth century literary works and radio broadcasts could indeed serve as a model for normative usage. Today the situation has changed, not every literary work and not every radio and television broadcast can serve as a model for the

normative use of language. The sphere of strict adherence to the norms of the language has narrowed significantly, only some programs and periodicals can be used as examples of literary-standardized speech.

B.N. Golovin defined the norm as a functional property of language skills: "The norm is a property of the functioning structure of the language, created by the team using it due to the constantly acting need for better mutual understandin.

Without communication, neither an individual nor human society as a whole can exist. Communication for a person is his habitat. Without communication, it is impossible to form a person's personality, his upbringing, intellectual development, adaptation to life. Communication is necessary for people, both in the process of joint work, and to maintain interpersonal relationships, recreation, emotional relief, intellectual and artistic creativity. The ability to communicate is both a natural quality of every person, given by nature, and a difficult art, involving constant improvement. Communication is a process of interaction between individuals and social groups, in which there is an exchange of activities, information, experience, skills and results of activities. In the process of communication: social experience is transmitted and assimilated; there is a change in the structure and essence of interacting subjects; a variety of human personalities is formed; socialization takes place.

In conclusion: The culture of speech is - the ability to speak and write correctly, as well as to use language means in accordance with the goals and conditions of communication. Correct is speech that is consistent with the norms of the literary language (pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary). A true culture of speech is achieved by skillful and appropriate use of vocabulary of different styles, a variety of syntactic constructions; in oral speech, the richness of intonation is especially valuable. It is necessary to have a clear idea of the stylistic gradation of linguistic elements, of their different purposes. When characterizing the totality of knowledge, skills and speech skills of a person, the culture of his speech is defined as follows: it is such a choice and such an organization of language means that, in a certain communication situation, while observing modern language norms and ethics of communication, can provide the greatest effect in achieving the set communicative tasks. For the successful implementation of communicative tasks, an understanding of the areas of communication is necessary. In the typology of functional varieties of language, a special place is occupied by the language of fiction and colloquial speech. As functional

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styles, which in their linguistic organization have significant differences, both from the language of fiction and from colloquial speech, official business, scientific and journalistic are distinguished .

Based on the foregoing, the following conclusion can be drawn: the main thing for the culture of speech is the observance of language norms and rules for the use of verbal language means, which allow you to comply with communicative norms in a given situation. The main thing in the field of effective communication is correctly delivered communication..

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